

Stakeholders' Assessment of the Role of Community-Based Media Practice in Grassroots Development

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Abstract

Community-based media are socially oriented and driven by democratic principles. A major idea behind the concept is to empower marginalised communities to enable them define and manage their own development. Over the years, community-based media have struggled to their feet in Nigeria despite that the roots of media development in the country could be traced to the community level. This study examined the views of stakeholders on the role of community-based media practice in driving development at the grassroots level using survey method with interview guide as basic instrument. Data were gathered through using face to face interactive interviews with editors/publishers of select community newspapers in South-west Nigeria. Findings revealed that stakeholders were in agreement that community-based media are capable of bringing development closer to the people by getting them involved in determining the direction and focus of development goals. However, respondents noted that the model of Community-based media practice currently obtainable in Nigeria does not promote communal participation, consequently leaving it in the hands of a few Individuals who often follow their political and economic profit blueprint which relegates the collective good of the community to the background to the background. The study concluded that for rural communities to benefit fully from community-based media practice, stakeholders must embrace the right model of community media practice that must focus on people's interest and community development.

Keywords: Community-based media practice, Stakeholders' assessment, Grassroots development, Community development, South-West Nigeria

Introduction

Community media practice promotes civic and cultural literacy, encourages effective political participation and inclusion, and brings about socio-economic development at community level. Community media represents a crucial input in development processes, playing an important role in democratisation, social struggles, and in raising awareness. But often, community journalists and media owners face difficulties related to finance, infrastructure and policy, which in many cases tend to favour bigger and more established media institutions owned by government and wealthy private individuals. Seidu et al. (2011) posited that community media can play a significant role at the grassroots level for rural development, with issues of poverty, agriculture, gender inequality, education, social problems among others becoming the focus. Even though these issues attract attention from bigger media organisations, it is believed that the proximity of community media to individuals within local settings helps in projecting them to those in authority. The people get involved through behavioural change approaches that bring about needed improvement in key areas of their personal and communal lives.

The history of media practice in Nigeria is known to have begun as a community effort by missionaries who sought majorly to inform and educate locales through community publications. The incursion of politics into media practice over time in the country brought about a rapid shift in focus and approach, while the establishment of state owned media houses stifled the continued development of community media practice. Whereas government favoured its own media establishments through policy, infrastructure and adequate operational resources, community media lagged behind in the hands of individuals with limited resources despite its strategic role in driving

development at the grassroots. The result is a near comatose community media segment that has seen the demise of many local media outfits.

However, with the continuous advancement in media and technology in a fast paced globalised village-world, the focus of modern media practice tends to be more on cities and semi-urban areas. Media outfits have concentrated more on news and entertainment packages that suits urban dwellers, with little or near nothing to cater for lesser educated rural community dwellers. This situation has further aggravated the need for revitalisation of community-based media practice through which members of respective communities could connect on various fronts and participate actively in efforts that promote the development of their local communities. Communication, which is the heart of media practice, is seen as the live wire for achieving communal development in every given setting. As Aruma (2018) observed, every community development initiative as a social development project requires effective communication among various groups of people who are involved in such development project in participating communities. This implies that community-based media can accelerate communication among participating communities and their members, connecting them with other stakeholders to drive community development initiatives.

Communication in community development focuses on enhancing the interaction between the people, promoting change that will impact positively on improving the living conditions of members of participating communities and other stakeholders with whom they work to actualize their dream (Aruma, 2018). In the views of Fasel (2000) communication is imperative to make ventures easy and to ensure that all will participate in the society. Communication certainly elicits collective action of project participants in community development projects in participating communities. It is therefore imperative to keep communication channels open among all project participants and organisations involved in community development initiatives. While communication channels are not limited to media channels, the media certainly function actively as organs of communication in sensitisation, mobilisation and in driving participation. Understanding the role of community-based media in grassroots development therefore can help community members and other stakeholders intensify efforts in revitalising moribund community-based media outfits and to seek needed partnerships to keep them going while also devising strategies to establish new ones. Recent events denote that community media are often neglected by policy makers. One of the main reasons for this is the lack of a shared understanding of what community media are and how they can contribute to an active citizenship.

According to Hollander et al. (2002), community media provide public communication made available to everyone within a specific context: the community, understood not only as a geographical setting but primarily as a social setting. Community media are devoted to the 'reproduction and representation of common interests', and 'the community serves as a frame of reference for a shared interpretation' (Hollander et al., 2002, p. 23). Emphasis is on the symbolic experience or the transformation of 'private individual experience into public collective experience' (Hollander et al. 2002, p. 26). Consequently, it is imperative for stakeholders to assess the role of community-based media and highlight how it is beneficial to community members especially at the grassroots level.

Literature review

The Nigerian media started in 1859 with the establishment of a community newspaper known as *Iwe Iroyin fun Awon Ara Egba* for the purpose of fostering development among Yoruba people of Abeokuta among other reasons. Since then, the media in Nigeria have continued to serve as development agent in different areas of the nation's socio-political and economic advancement except in rural communities where the media have often been brought to be used to mobilise the people to serve the interest of the urban based political elites. This is against the spirit of community development, therefore, community media should exist as part of the community itself not a facility to be brought in by an external agency/individuals with our prior assessment and consultation (Oso,

2003; Raufu, 2014; Abiola, 2023). This position of Oso, Raufu and Abiola underscores the need for a robust, community-development oriented community-based media practice.

Community-based media practice

The term ‘community’ has been defined differently by authors and scholars of varied backgrounds. A simplified description of the concept could mean a group of people living in the same place or having a particular characteristic in common. MacQueen et al (2001) defined community as a group of people with diverse characteristics who are linked by social ties, share common perspectives, and engage in joint action in geographical locations or settings. Another definition refers to community as a social, religious, occupational, or other group sharing common characteristics or interests and perceived or perceiving itself as distinct in some respect from the larger society within which it exists. This second definition alludes to groups such as business community, community of scholars, professional community, church community, virtual community, international community, urban community, rural community and so on. For a proper contextualisation of community in this study therefore, it’s imperative to make clear that the concept is used in reference to rural African communities situated within Nigerian states. In most cases, popular definitions given by scholars in advanced societies do not truly reflect the typical under-developed African rural community. In advanced societies, rural areas refer to the countryside, with serene atmosphere and a fervour of something cultural/traditional that may not be obtainable in the hustle and bustle of city life. However, in the African context, a rural community depicts situations of poverty, hunger, unemployment, non-availability of infrastructure, illiteracy and lack of basic social amenities among others. Community in this sense would refer to a group of people living in villages outside the cities, towns and state capitals where living conditions are relatively poor. Some discernible features of such community are the closeness of the people to natural environment, greater social homogeneity, smallness of the communal aggregates, predominance of agricultural occupations, and relatively sparse population (Aneto & Aneto, 2010). In Nigeria, dwellers in such communities make up more than 75 per cent of the entire population, yet they appear to have been relegated to the background by the government and the media alike, which heightens the need for community media within such environs as to attract government’s attention and synergise the people towards achieving needed developments.

The word media refers to a combination of different communication channels through which various information, education, entertainment and news are spread. The physical form includes newspapers, magazines, journals and books, while the electronic forms are television, radio, telephone and the internet (Atton, 2015). Whereas mass media refers to reaching a large number of people simultaneously with a message, community media is purely meant for a particular community. This implies that the audience of a community-based media is much less and the services cater for the needs of a special group of people or community (Atton, 2015). According to the International Association for Media and Communication (IAMCR), community-based media is the community communication and alternative media section which focuses on media that originates, circulates and resonates from the sphere of civil society. Rennie (2006) asserted that this type of media is usually run on a not-for-profit basis and provides community members with an opportunity to participate in the production process, which is why it is often referred to as local media, participatory media, and citizen media, among others. Community-based media works as alternative to the mainstream and corporate media while interacting with both, highlighting the needs of the people, which government and mainstream media could have failed to notice.

Community-based media practice thrives within a suitable environment. Burckley (2011) observed that despite the growing recognition of community media worldwide, there remains a need to promote and defend the right of communities to own and to operate their own community media. Buckley noted that conditions favouring community media are most likely to be achieved in a

context of deepening democracy and the adoption of a public interest approach to the development of free, independent and pluralistic media (Buckley et al., 2008). These ingredients are practically lacking in most African nations including Nigeria, which accounts for why the practice of community media in the real sense of it has remained difficult.

Grassroots development

Grassroots development refers to community development from the bottom to the top. The term is used to describe the process by which disadvantaged people organise themselves to improve the social, cultural and economic well-being of their families, communities and societies. Leonardi (2014) averred that the concept is based on the premise that the key to sustainable democracies, equitable societies and prosperous economies is a people-oriented strategy that stresses bottom-top participation. Although government from the top provides needed resources for development projects at grassroots level, the idea is that such projects will add more value if it originates based on needs of the people as articulated by them. For years development theorists believed that mass media were ideal instruments to bring development to rural societies. Fact as it may be, the media only drives development as far as the people in such rural societies are carried along. As Adesemoye and Acheme (2021) pointed out that development implies deliberate and carefully managed interventions in the social, political and economic spheres of rural societies, which should follow models based on the preservation and autonomy of local and traditional knowledge systems. This no doubt requires grassroots democratic participation in setting development objectives based on local needs, indigenous cultural and ecological values rather than purely economic perspective to growth. This type of development approach is what experts refer to as grassroots, popular or people centred development, it promotes creative and empowering solutions to many problems that mainstream development models have not been able to tackle (Morgan-Trimmer, 2014). Brohman (1996) suggested that this approach represents perhaps the best alternative for creating development appropriate to the needs and interests of the majority in developing countries.

Grassroots development promotes people's well-being and empowers self-help groups to expand and make their own choices and bring about change. Development at the grassroots will be achieved faster people living within rural communities have the freedom to make their own decisions and their own development priorities, draw their own plans, implement and ensure a fair share of the fruits of their work for each member of their community. Many have argued that direct public or private investments in rural areas could help drive development at the grassroots level. However, research has suggested that more would be needed to ensure that public and private investments in rural areas contribute directly to the uplifting of living standards of grassroots populations. As Morgan-Trimmer (2014) noted, the trickle-down effect of such investment will not just happen in the absence of relevant policies that would ensure maximum participation of grassroots populations, not only in the development process, but equally importantly in the equitable sharing of the benefits of development. Consequently as Heredero (in Fernandez, 1980) pointed out, people's participation will go a long way to distribute wealth more equitably, doing away with the present inequalities and providing a more equitable base for a better system of social relations; this statement having identified the effects of a genuine participatory development approach leave us with a more fundamental question as to how this process can take place.

Theoretical framework

The study examines two relevant theories which are: the Development Media Theory and Democratic Participant Theory. The Development Media Theory places emphasis on the involvement of the grassroots in the communication flow where the press is placed as a tool on the path of development. The Democratic Participant Theory calls for an end to inherent commercialisation, bureaucracy and professional hegemony that prevent mass media from performing their true social functions.

On one hand, the Development Media Theory presupposes that journalism practitioners should learn to understand the views and aspirations of the grassroots people and transmit them to government thereby assuming the voice of the voiceless (Raufu, 2014). The basic tenets of the theory, according to McQuail (1978) includes that: the media must accept and carry out developmental tasks in line with nationally established policies; Freedom of the media should be open to economic priorities and developmental needs of the society; Media should stress links with geographically, culturally, politically and economically close communities. The theory advocates purposive use of the media towards the attainment of defined socio-political and economic goals. The theory is relevant to this study by virtue of its focus on grassroots development which is also the focus of this study.

The study is however anchored on the Democratic Participant Theory. The theory is a reaction to the libertarian and social responsibility theories which failed to actively provide social benefits, despite their promising constructs and propositions (Folarin, 1998). The democratic participant media theory is hinged on media multiplicity, the localisation of media practice and horizontal involvement and interaction of people with the media. The society has the right to information, right to feedback and right to interaction. In the understanding of McQuail (2005), media monopoly by government or private conglomerates is an enemy of the democratic participant theory, in the sense that the theory works against centralism of media institutions.

The proposition of the theory favours an engagement between the government and the media in charting a course for national development. Therefore, media must be positively positioned and used for national economic development and social harmony. As much as there is mutual cooperation between the government and the media, there is a capacity for government to sanction the media when they display irresponsibility. This proposition is similar to that of the development media theory since both places the control of the media in the hands of government when national interest is at stake.

It has been noted by Moemeka (2000) that this theory fits the professional practices of community-based media in a typical African setting. This submission makes the theory desirable in this study since the focus is to see the contributions of community-based media to the development of local communities where they operate. The cannibalisation of the community-based media ownership is responsible for its endangered situation in Nigeria and where a theory seeks an end to government bureaucracy and private ownership, it will definitely support the growth and development of the third-tier of media ownership, which is the community-based ownership of media in Nigeria.

Objective of the study

This study set out to examine stakeholders' views on the role that community-based media practice has played and can play in driving development at the grassroots communities in South-West, Nigeria.

Methodology

The study is a qualitative research. It adopted survey method and used interview guide as basic instrument to generate data from editors/publishers of selected community newspapers in South-west Nigeria. The key informants who took part in interview sessions with researchers were five editors and publishers of the selected Community-Based Newspapers. They included editors and publishers from *Oriwu Sun Newspaper*, *Ibarapa Newspaper*, *Ilupeju Today* and *Osun Defender*. Data gathering was between April and July, 2022 and the data were thematically analysed

Data presentation and discussion of findings

All the key informants agree that Community-Based media are small-scale, non-profit enterprises with the aim to reflect and service the interest of a specific local community. This aligns with the

position of Oso (2003), Raufu (2014) and Abiola (2023) that an ideal community-based media should give voice to rural communities that lack access to mainstream media by delivering contents that promote the development agenda of such communities, which before then have been neglected.

Key informants in the study are also of the view that although most community media outfits contend with issues relating to financial sustainability, weak technical skills, low professional journalistic standards and undemocratic political systems, they however contended that community media practice contribute to the development of democracy, advancing pro-poor development agenda, raising awareness of social struggles and reaching marginalised groups. They observed that community-based media, usually for the local people, run and owned by them, enhances their capacity to work together to tackle collective political and economic problems bedevilling the community. This ideal situation whereby communities jointly owned and operate media outfits at the grassroots level is still not in force; rather the model that operates presently in many Nigerian communities is one where community-based media are driven by individual initiatives. The problem with this model, apart from the fact that it lacks major ingredients of Community-based media practice, is that it sometimes serves the political and or financial interests of those who finance or champion them.

While the respondents agreed that there is need for improvement in the operations of Community-Based media, they contended that the present mode of operation still favours local communities in many ways. A key informant from Ikorodu averred that there were many stories *Oriwu Sun* published that had brought progress to Ikorodu.

According to him, “*Oriwu Sun* will give full page to tell a story in Ikorodu unlike national newspapers that will write two or three paragraphs to report the same story. Other media both broadcast and print consult *Oriwu Sun* for stories relating to Ikorodu community, we have published stories that have to do with the socio-economic welfare of the people of Ikorodu, we have sensitized the government to basic necessities of life for the people; electricity, potable water, healthcare services, road construction, environmental issues, security, promotion of cultural values and festivity. We have also made our lawmakers in political mobilizations, sensitization and education. We use to give prominence to stories that have to do with the lives of our people. We call the attention of governments to issues that basically concerned the people through some stories that may not be adequately given prominence by national newspapers, which we give prominence in *Oriwu Sun*”.

He further noted that through such stories, the attention of Lagos State government had been called to the needs of the people in Ikorodu community on several occasions, while the government has also partnered with the newspaper to educate and sensitise inhabitants of the community on certain government policies and plans. *Oriwu Sun* has often been used as an organ of public enlightenment on certain crucial issues, providing community service and social responsibility to the people of Ikorodu. The newspaper always based its reports on the key elements of news like; timeliness, fact, proximity, importance and personality. “Every published story is factual and objective”.

Another respondent opined that community media essentially gives a voice to the voiceless; it highlights issues that concerns the host community; such stories that will not attract mainstream media attention since they are more concerned with issues affecting the entire country. “It is a type of journalism that gives prominence to proximity”. So, it has contributed to grassroots development because *Ibarapa News* reports local issues and meets concerned authorities to provide solutions to community problems.

“Before now, Ibarapa community depends on Ibadan for everything relating to media and information. There was no smooth information flow in Ibarapa and the people do not even know what's happening around them in their community. But now, the newspaper has reporters in Eruwa, Igbo ora, Idere, Igangan, and Ibadan. The person in Ibadan feeds them with happenings around there, others report from their local communities. So, people in Ibarapa can get information of happenings in Ibarapa land and in Oyo State generally. In the light of this, *Ibarapa News* gives the people locally sourced news that connected to the development of the community. “I am proud to inform you that it was our paper that facilitated restoration of electricity to Eruwa and some other towns in Ibarapa land through our news stories”.

A key informant from Osogbo also noted that *Osun Defender* is known for enriching news dissemination and creation of job as there are different segments of people working in the newspaper outfit. *Osun Defender* gives special reports on a particular sector or segment in the society to draw government attention. The newspaper always discharges its social responsibility to the society effectively. There are different columns in *Osun Defender* that talk about health, sport, business, environment, entertainment and politics. The major difference between the newspaper and others with national coverage is that it operates in a community and gives prominence to local stories as it affects the people of Osogbo community and the entire Osun State. *Ilupeju Today* was also noted to have contributed immensely to the community by reporting “smaller things that government does to impact lives at the grassroots level”. This is in line with the position of Milan (2009) who argued that community media represents a crucial input in development processes, playing an important role in democratisation, social struggles, and awareness rising. Similarly, Mhagama (2014) corroborated the point that community-based media empower people at the grassroots to have control over the communication system that serves them and that marginalised communities are also empowered to define and manage their own development since such outfits are meant to be driven by democratic principles which are socially and not profit oriented. Mhagama also supported that community participation and access are the major tenets upon which community media are credited.

All key informants in this study highlighted relative contributions of mostly community-based Newspapers to local development, but they worried about ownership and profiteering which they consider as requiring extensive consideration by government and stakeholders. Most community-based media in Nigeria are owned and operated by individuals who either established them for profit or to promote their political ideologies. This negates the idea of community-oriented model of community media practice and it has also over time somehow impeded the ability of Community-Based media to deliver needed gains to rural areas since the self-interest of proprietors could overshadow that of the entire community. Mhagama (2014) further highlighted community participation as key indices through which the success of community-based media can be measured, noting that the requirement of community participation ensures that members of the community are involved in running the media outfits in such activities as includes: election of leadership, policy-making, management, selection and provisions for programming, production and external representation of the media establishment. It is important therefore to note that the gains of community-based media practice at the grassroots in Nigeria is still one-sided if at all, until a holistic approach that guarantees total community involvement is embraced.

Conclusion

The study assessed stakeholders’ view of the role community-based media play in driving grassroots development. Based on the revelations from the stakeholders assessment of the role played by community-based media in the development of the grassroots communities, the study concluded that community based media have contributed to the development of their communities in the past and they still have the potentials to drive overall development of rural dwellers in the areas of infrastructure, education, politics and economy if a community-oriented model of community-based media are established and practiced. Although the study identified key areas of economic, political and infrastructural developments accelerated through community-based Newspapers, a major area identified by key informants to be lagging and needing to be addressed is in community dwellers’ participation in the everyday business of community media in their locality. For any media organisation to be regarded as community-based, managers of such media must find a way to get the community people involved as stakeholders in the media.

Recommendations

There are different models of community-based media with different participants having the leeway to adopt an appropriate participatory approach for their circumstance. Therefore, this study recommends that managers of community-based media should endeavour to get community members to participate in community media in all relevant ways. The ubiquity of smart devices has made citizen journalism easier. In this regard, the researchers recommend that community members can be made to function as reporters, writers, graphic content creators and even in actual production. The holistic development craved by communities is in the hands of the community members within the community, hence, the study recommends bringing them together to work for a common goal to serve as catalyst to desired development outcomes both in the immediate and nearest future.

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